

STAKEHOLDERS' INVOLVEMENT IN SCHOOL-BASED PROGRAMS OF GOSOON ELEMENTARY SCHOOL, CARMEN, AGUSAN DEL NORTE

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Abstract: Participation of stakeholders, and consultation of citizens are nowadays a key element in policy decision making. It is generally recognized as the main indicator of good governance. Active involvement in the decision-making process was never a privilege of a closed circle, an “elite” of civil servants and professional politicians in the community of Gosoon. Consultation of social partners, socio-economic organizations and other partners in the community is an old tradition and what is included today is the participation of student leaders in decision making process. Stakeholders and citizens no longer accept to be the subject of policy without a certain degree of involvement and consultation. They want to make their voice heard and policy makers have to listen.

An experimental research design was used in the study to determine the involvement of stakeholders in school-based programs. The questionnaire was the main tool used to determine the involvement of the stakeholders in school – based programs based on the PESTEL framework. It was submitted to the principal and a planning officer for content validation. Some items were refined based on their comments and suggestions. The questionnaire was tried out to the stakeholders of another barangay for its reliability testing using the test-retest method. A focus group discussion was conducted for the qualitative portion where the stakeholders were interviewed on their values and beliefs that helped in the implementation of the school – based projects.

The overall mean which means that stakeholders have “high” participation level in the school -based programs. The indicator with the highest mean of 3.49 is on political factors; the lowest mean of 3.38 is on technological factors.

It further shows that the stakeholders are highly involved in political aspect which implies that they are aware of the issues that are related to education. On the other hand, they fall short on technological aspect but this is not an issue because still learners are given ample time to use the computers for easy access of information for their assignments, projects, etc. This also implies that stakeholders are politically inclined and aware of the duties and responsibilities as stakeholders.

Keywords: Stakeholder’s Involvement.

1. INTRODUCTION

Participation of stakeholders, and consultation of citizens are nowadays a key element in policy decision making. It is generally recognized as the main indicator of good governance. Active involvement in the decision-making process was never a privilege of a closed circle, an “elite” of civil servants and professional politicians in the community of Gosoon. Consultation of social partners, socio-economic organizations and other partners in the community is an old tradition and what is included today is the participation of student leaders in decision making process. Stakeholders and citizens no

longer accept to be the subject of policy without a certain degree of involvement and consultation. They want to make their voice heard and policy makers have to listen.

Participation/involvement makes better policy in two ways. First, in a technical sense, the real know how, the real expertise is on the field, and secondly, participation during the decision- making process that creates a platform for the choice of policy and thus, for the implementation of the policy. It is very important to have stakeholder's participation and involvement in education policy making for the successful implementation of school - based projects. According to Saxene (2014), the involvement of the broader community of the school improved communication and public understanding and allowed the incorporation of the perspectives, experiences and expertise of participating community members to improve or refine proposals, strategies or processes.

The involvement of the broader community of a school leads to higher academic performance and school improvement. When schools, parents, families and communities work together to support learning, students feel more encouraged, attend school more regularly and take part in higher-level programs. This involvement is the key to addressing school drop-out crisis and strong partnership foster higher educational aspirations and more motivated students.

Countries and governments prefer to work with stakeholders and interest groups to examine the benefits where stakeholders, policy makers and experts come together where they meet in the context of a formal advisory body. In this manner, consultation processes become more transparent, and more efficient, that can give a boost to the development of the abilities of every learner.

In order to achieve the objectives of the Education for All (EFA), the Department of Education is pursuing policy reforms under the Basic Education Sector Reform Agenda (BESRA). Key Reform Thrust 1 (KRT1) of BESRA is School-Based Management (SBM). With SBM, several enabling policies were formulated such as the School Governing Council (SGC); conduct of Assessment of Level of Practice; School Improvement Planning (SIP); and reporting of accomplishments through School Reports Cards (SRCs). These policies are supported by a budget line item in the General Appropriations Act (GAA) for the installation of SBM in all public elementary and secondary schools. With this, the SBM had been revised to better highlight the learner as the center of SBM practice; to encompass the diverse realities of learning contexts defined and uniquely occurring within specific geographic, social, cultural, economic, political, and environmental make-up of the contemporary society; to enhance commitment of education stakeholders at all levels to their responsibilities and accountabilities in realizing the education outcomes for children; and to improve the school system's capacity to be on track in achieving the Education for All/Millennium Development Goals and sustain good performance (Department of Education, 2012).

With this, the Department of Education (DepEd) has been implementing projects, programs and activities (PPA) that realize SBM and other sound philosophical and legal frameworks of the department. These PPAs include Brigada Eskwela, Every Child-A-Reader Program, School First Initiative; Child-Friendly School System; Project WATCH (We Advocate Time Consciousness and Honesty); and Adopt-A-School Program. It has been observed that although the schools are doing their best in making linkages with different school stakeholders, it has been reported to have a low involvement of stakeholders on school-initiated activities. It is for the reason that this study was conceptualized.

An effective stakeholder strategy mitigates the risk of the challenges that schools face by ensuring that they have understood and responded to the needs of the stakeholders to make school plans to be successful. By developing stronger and more constructive relationships with our stakeholders, at both national and local levels, schools will ultimately achieve longer term efficient delivery of primary outputs. Hence, this study is about the involvement of the stakeholders and define what is their function to improve the school programs for better use. The primary goal of teachers is to promote learning, inspire students to bring out their best and help them become productive members of the community.

It has been observed that some teachers are even more popular than others among students because of building good relationships with students, and by treating them with respect. However, this ideal situation would not be possible without the help and support of the stakeholders. Thus, a healthy relationship between the teachers and stakeholders is important, as this enables everybody to harmoniously work together, which has a positive impact on the development of students.

Stakeholders play an important role in managing schools. They are the partners of the school leaders in making the schools conducive to teaching and learning. In crafting the school improvement plan, stakeholders are members of the working committee who look into their involvement in making plans with the school to make the school conducive to learning. They are also responsible for the achievement of the learning outcomes through their active participation in school activities, programs and projects. The external stakeholders are included as members of the team to evaluate the SBM level of practice.

School heads are empowered by virtue of RA 9155 also known as the Basic Education Act of 2001, where school heads/leaders can make innovations on the strategies and techniques to raise school performance. The involvement and partnership of pupils, parents, teachers, and the community is very evident in the present situation of Gosoon Elementary School, wherein projects are implemented through the collaborative efforts of all. The school pathway was cemented through the joint efforts of parents, and the Barangay personnel; the school stage was finished and is ready to use through the collaboration of parents and the Barangay; the ICT / e-classroom and window grill that secures school's facilities were realized through the support of alumni of the school; and lately, school bags and supplies were given to pupils by a sponsor who never forgets to look back where he came from. These endeavors are just examples of the participation of the stakeholders in school.

On the other hand, stakeholders are given tribute as recognition of their contribution and gratitude for their willingness to share their resources to the school graduation and alumni homecomings. Indeed, great partnership has an incredible impact on the successful implementation of programs and projects in education, hence, this study which according to Henry Ford, "coming together is a beginning; keeping together is progress; working together is success."

Review of Literature and Studies

This section presents the pertinent literature and studies that have some bearing on the present study.

Stakeholder involvement involves working with people and using the resources as they are and helping them to work together to realize agreed ends and goals. A skilled manager looks for ways in which the interests and ability of each individual can contribute to the good of the whole. The head teacher tries to create in the school an environment in which this can happen. Given that the government has provided compulsory and free primary education for all, it is imperative that the school management involves all stakeholders in the decision making process. According to the Ministry of Education (2010), the government allocates every child in the public primary schools shillings 1704. The stakeholders in the education sector are concerned with the poor performance while the MOE is doing their best to alleviate the problem. The implementation of stakeholder involvement in school management practices is expected to enhance performance in the primary schools. This study attempted to establish the level of stakeholder involvement and how it influences academic excellence.

There have been several studies on parents' social and cultural capital as significant components in determining children's educational outcomes (Bukodi & Goldthorpe, 2012; Dufur & Troutman, 2013; Vincent, Rollock, Ball, & Gillborn, 2012). Social capital is the knowledge parents attain through relationships which provide information on resources available to support their children's academic progress (Leithwood & Patrician, 2015). When families adhered to norms which included value systems, ways of thinking and modes of behavior which were considered acceptable in specific settings by the dominant culture their social capital increased (Edgerton, & Roberts, 2014; Winkle-Wagner & Rachelle, 2010).

These families became familiar with how the school system worked and were able to access what they needed from the school system. They knew whom to contact when their children were having problems at school, they were assertive in school communications, and they were knowledgeable about how to assist their children's learning in school (Waite, 2013; Wegmann & Bowen, 2010). Although similar to social capital, cultural capital has explicit distinctions. Cultural capital is defined as the capacity of knowledge an individual possesses as a member of a particular cultural group (Worrell, 2014). This form of capital is inherited from parents and is considered intergenerational. (Potter & Roska, 2013). This inheritance may take place in two ways, by exposure to parents' cultural capital, or by parents' making a conscience effort to transfer their cultural capital to their children (Kraaykamp & Eijck, 2010). The cultural capital framework identified behaviors and norms which schools valued. When cultural capital was a part of children's habitus, or way of life, it was evidenced in children's mannerisms, language, and their knowledge (Trainor, 2010). Children's familiarity with the acceptable behaviors and the norms of the dominant culture were perceived as high achieving and

received preferential treatment from teachers (Jaeger, 2011). Gaddis (2013) maintained that the attainment of cultural capital was significant because it changed students' views about their ability to achieve academic progress and their value of education. The effects of cultural capital manifested in three ways; children of families with cultural capital are: better learners familiarized with abstract and intellectual issues, and approached by teachers more positively. Because of their familiarity with dominant culture norms, these children fared better in school than children from disadvantaged backgrounds (Gaddis, 2013).

Mostly studies agreed that school-based parental involvement in children's education had a generally positive outcome for student's achievement. However, while most indicated that it was school policy that needed to change in order to involve more parents and school policy means nothing unless it is backed up by action on the school's part to include parents and make them feel that their contributions are worthwhile. If parents themselves had faced negative experience in their schooling life, they may already have formed a negative view of schools. This type of parents may view their children's school as hostile territory. The barriers in way of parents' involvement seems into two forms one is general and other is specific. Both the forms of obstacles influence parental involvement. It is the teacher and administrators who can play a lead role in helping parents overcoming these obstacles. By opening communication and developing an open-door policy, parents will feel more welcome participation as stakeholder. Teachers also need to overcome their own assumptions about parents and help to foster an alliance with parents

The beliefs of teachers and administrators on parental involvement can have a vitalizing or demoralizing influence on school culture (Hamel, Shaw, & Taylor, 2013). When teachers' efforts to involve parents were unsuccessful their self-efficacy was impacted, and they questioned their ability to teach and connect with parents (Mahmood, 2013). Administrators have the potential to create partnerships between schools and home that value and accept parental involvement (Young, Austin, & Growe, 2013). Efficacious administrators recognized that their definition of parental involvement differed from the diverse population they served and considered the cultures of parents and students when developing parental involvement programs. The lenses of efficacy and sociocultural capital become even more important as the cultural diversity of an area or school increases.

Parental involvement influences students' academic progress, however, the ability to involve parents remains a concern (Reece, Staudte, & Ogle, 2013). Diverse populations in urban schools have resulted in cultural differences regarding the term parental involvement. The literature review presents research regarding the theoretical framework of self-efficacy, social capital, and culture capital and their influence on parental involvement.

Most parents like to support their children's academic progress, but they are not clear about how to effectively achieve academic goals (Nelson & Guerra, 2014). Fan, Williams, and Walters (2011) examined parental involvement programs in public schools and found efforts to increase parental involvement planned the same activities for parents across ethnic groups. No consideration was given to how academic progress was attained in culturally diverse groups (Marshall, Shah, & Donato, 2012). Walker, Ice, and Hoover-Dempsey (2011) reported that Latino parents valued education and expected their children to do well in school. However, culturally some Latino parents believed that it was disrespectful to engage in a teaching role with their children (Walker, Ice, & Hoover-Dempsey, 2011). Khalilfa (2010) contended that schools devalued the social capital of Black students, and often viewed Black students as confrontational. The relationship teachers and school personnel had with Black students was the same relationship they had with Black parents resulting in parents' negative perspectives of schools (McGrady & Reynolds, 2013). Consequently, minority parents did not feel welcomed at schools and believed that schools did not want them to be involved, and were likely to be less involved (Williams & Sanchez, 2013). Therefore, schools should systematically learn the beliefs of minority parents to increase parental involvement (Gillanders, McKinney, & Ritchie, 2012).

On the other hand, Vera et al. (2012) posited that educated immigrant parents understood the United States schooling system and were not concerned with interfering with teachers' instruction, but were aware of the importance of communicating with teachers. These parents were aware of cultural expectations and made the most of the resources provided by schools to assist in supporting their children's education (Vera et al., 2012). Yet, there remained a population of parents who maintained their cultural beliefs about their role in their children's education. These parents continued to be a source of contention among educators who considered these parents uninvolved and unconcerned about their children's education (Vera et al., 2012). Educators were frustrated by the lack of parental involvement by minority

families in public schools, yet schools continued to develop parental involvement programs which marginalized low socio-economic and minority parents while providing support and resources for parents of White and middle- class children (Kavanagh & Hickey, 2013).

In contrast, parental involvement increased when educators valued the cultural capital parents and students brought to school by taking the time to learn how students and parents viewed the world (Bernhard, 2010). When educators became knowledgeable about diverse cultural values, they were able to interpret parents' involvement in a more informed, less evaluative way (Patel & Corter, 2013). In so doing, schools provided parents the social capital needed to make schools a place where parents felt comfortable and were able to participate in education (Duran & Perez, 2013) However, when schools merely accepted that cultural differences existed, schools preserved the control of privileges by the dominant culture (Anderson, 2012). Hashmi and Akhter (2013) maintained that parents were considered involved when they communicated with teachers and when they engaged in activities at home which supported their children's academic progress.

However, the definition of parental involvement remains ambiguous and may be viewed differently by parents, students, and teachers, and may differ between schools and geographic locations (Lam & Ducreux, 2013) Perspectives on parental involvement starting at pre-kindergarten level through middle school level concluded that teachers and school administrators from urban area schools had different understandings of parental involvement (Graves & Wright, 2011; Williams & Sanchez, 2012). Administrators' and teachers' definitions of parental involvement tended to ensure the success of the school while disregarding the needs of the families which schools served and observed that most definitions of parental involvement focused on activities that were visible to school personnel and did not consider parental involvement which took place at home. Nevertheless, theorists and researchers agreed that parents are a child's first teacher, and a driving force in a child's attainment of educational success (Goodall & Montgomery, 2014). Parents were involved in their children's learning from the time children were learning to talk, walk, and learning how to interact with others. Before a child enrolls in school, parents would have spent more than of 43,800 hours with their child. When a child enters school, a child spends 1,260 hours with an educator in comparison to the 7,490 hours spent with parents. More importantly, parental involvement before children entered school positioned children on an academic trajectory. The enduring influence of parental involvement should compel educators to involve parents early in students' education for optimal students' academic progress.

The stakeholder concept aims to coordinate the multiple relationships involved Freeman (2010) and assumes that managerial decisions and actions are the key factors that influence organizational-stakeholder relationships.

While the principal's role is critical, other school cultural characteristics are important. In their study on teacher work life, Bauch and Goldring (2010) found out that creating a caring atmosphere and requiring parent volunteering seem to have a large effect on promoting parent participation as viewed by teachers. In addition, their study suggested that if the school itself is a supportive environment for teachers to work in, teachers are more likely to provide parents with information. Another school culture characteristic, trust, is also a significant factor for collaboration among school staff and with the greater community. Tschannen-Moran (2010) found out that when school administrators collaborated with teachers, and when teachers collaborated with each other, they both indicated higher levels of trust. Similarly, when school staff collaborated with parents, each group indicated a greater level of trust. Consequently, they found out that when schools and communities share a sense of purpose and exhibit greater levels of trust, there is more outside stakeholder influence in the school decision-making processes. Socially constructed norms institutionalize relationships among teachers, administrators, and schools that often lead to negative teacher reflections of parents who are not involved (at least visibly) in the development of their child's education (Pen'a 2010; Smrekar and Cohen-Vogel 2011). Although some principals and teachers assume that low levels of parental involvement reflect parents' low interest in their child's education, evidence indicates the opposite—that parents, including inner city, low-income parents, generally display positive attitudes toward their children's educational development (Patrikakou and Weissberg 2012).

Schools design more opportunities for some parents than others. Specifically, teachers working with higher-income parents indicate that their school offers more opportunities for involvement at the school level than do teachers working with lower-income parents (Bauch and Goldring 2010). Other studies suggested that parents do not know how to be productively involved in their children's education (Epstein and Dauber 2012). Because of the low levels of parental and

community involvement in some districts, it can be argued that most parents need direction and help from the schools in order to know how to be productively involved in their children's education. The policies, pressures, and programs to fill this void in meaningful ways are currently inadequate (Kruse and Louis 2010).

Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

The study was anchored on the Stakeholder Theory postulated by R. Edward Freeman (2010). It explains that organizations have relationships with many constituent groups ("stakeholders") that both affect and are affected by its decisions. It is concerned with the nature of these relationships in terms of processes as well as outcomes both for the organizations and stakeholders. The interests of the stakeholders have intrinsic value, and no set of interests is assumed to dominate the others. The theory sheds light on managerial decision-making processes. Social science scholars used the stakeholder theory to shed light on a variety of organizational phenomena, ranging from corporate social responsibility to value maximization and functions to the rise of government. A recent review of the stakeholder theory revealed the significant impact of the theory in academic/professional fields like management, accounting, marketing and finance (Parmar et al. 2010). With respect to the field of management, it was suggested that the areas in which the theory has had a stronger impact pertained to leadership, organizational effectiveness and human resources management. According to Scott (2010), the importance attributed to stakeholders, particularly external ones, is part and parcel of the move of organizations from close to open systems thus, stressing the criticality of the linkages with the environment.

In terms of the emergent role of external stakeholders in European higher education governance, Amara and Magalhães (2010), classified stakeholders into internal (members of the academic community) and external (outsiders), and highlight that the latter refers to the presence of representatives of the interests of the outside world in university governance. Furthermore, it was argued that the presence of such external representatives was designed to make higher education institutions more responsive to their surrounding environments.

The stakeholder approach identifies the stakeholders in the organization and describes methods by which management can address all issues from the stakeholders. Traditionally, shareholders are important and the company's primary goal is to put their needs first (shareholder theory). However, the Stakeholder theory reworked this by including employees, customer's suppliers competition, governmental bodies, unions etc. into the mix and stated that the company should be run not only for the benefit of shareholders but of stakeholders too. It is used to define the relevant stakeholders to each company and the conditions in which each group should be treated.

On the other hand, Benneworth and Jongbloed (2010) discussed the issue of stakeholder salience with respect to academic fields or knowledge domains and against the backdrop of society's valorization towards the skills being transmitted and the knowledge being produced/transferred by higher education institutions. They argued that the lower degree of policy attention is attributed to 'softer' fields like the humanities. However, they contended that the degree of responsiveness by higher education institutions to certain types of stakeholder groups does not evolve simply and functionally but in response to the networks of relationships in which they are situated.

Finally, the important attribute to stakeholder issues in contemporary higher education affairs across the globe is a reflection of the changing nature of the social pact between higher education and society. The discussion on the role of stakeholders makes a distinction between those internal to the system and outside parties likely to influence developments. There are actually four main audiences included in the internal group: the (professional) oligarchy, associated with the prestigious professional fields such as medicine and law; the scientific community at large, i.e. tenured scientific scholars; unionized lecturers, who hold full-time contracts at universities yet are little involved with research activities partly since they do not possess doctoral education; and academics employed throughout the private sector.

In addition to the four key groups of stakeholders, three other internal stakeholders are referred to by Balbachevsky. These are- student movements and unions; employees' unions; and the central administration. Student unions have gradually lost their power and influence over the broader political system - in the last 20 years. Their major priorities were to maintain public institutions tuition-free; expand the amount of public resources re-directed to the sector; and support democratic governance (one person, one vote) when it comes to electing the central administration. Notwithstanding, students still exercise considerable influence due to their partnerships with academic and employees' unions when it comes to the mobilization for radical action inside and outside the campus. Employees' unions represent the shared

interests of non-academic staff and are particularly concerned with issues pertaining to work conditions, including salaries and career trajectories. In addition, Balbachevsky (2017) reported that stakeholders play a prominent role in keeping universities tuition-free; sustaining an internal system of democratic governance; resisting any type of performance appraisal. The role of employees’ unions is particularly pronounced during electoral years, largely as a result of their collaborations with other unionized groups.

Given that school-based programs (and the interventions within) rely on a range of stakeholders, the extent to which these particular stakeholders engage in any intervention can impact on the overall direction and outcome of the program. Two key stakeholder groups are teachers and parents. For example, an intervention that has the contributions of parents would have a different focus and design (i.e. through a first-hand appreciation of how messages can be supported in the home environment) and potential for sustainability than one that does not. Therefore, stakeholder input and relations should be considered as a key part of planning, implementing and evaluating complex school-based programs (Pettigrew et al., 2012). In particular, the role parents and teachers take is critical for underpinning any intervention feasibility, acceptability and overall performance (Della Torre et al., 2010, Bruss et al., 2010, Downs et al., 2012).

Figure 1 shows the research flow. The level of involvement of the stakeholders in school – based programs is measured using the PESTEL framework (political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal).

Statement of the Problem

The study aimed to determine the stakeholders' involvement in school-based programs of Gosoon Elementary School, Carmen, Agusan del Norte.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions based on the PESTEL (political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal) framework.

1. What is the level of involvement of stakeholders in school – based programs in terms of:
 - 1.1 political factors;
 - 1.2 economic factors;
 - 1.3 social factors;
 - 1.4 technological factors;
 - 1.5 environmental factors; and
 - 1.6 legal factors?
2. What policies in the local and in the DepEd that contribute to the success of the school – based programs?
3. What values and beliefs of stakeholders that help in the implementation of the school – based programs?
4. What factors contribute most in the implementation of the school – based programs?
5. Based on the result of the study, what factors contribute most to improve the involvement of stakeholders in school – based programs?

Significance of the Study

The study will benefit the following.

School Head. The findings of the study will provide them with a clear understanding of the stakeholders' involvement in school – based programs of the learners to help them cope up with the challenges and provide quality learning to learners.

Teachers. The findings of the study will make them become aware of their contributions as they play a big part in the learning process and how it affects their teaching performance and their relationship with the stakeholders and become better teachers and citizens of the community.

Stakeholders. As beneficiaries of the study, the findings of the study may help them understand their involvement in school – based programs will contribute to the success of the programs.

Future Researchers. The findings of the study may provide them additional information on the topic being undertaken and consider other variables not included in the present study.

Definition of Terms

The following terms were defined operationally.

Economic Factors. It refers to the metrics that measure the health of the community, income of the stakeholders, unemployment rate and inflation.

Environmental factors. It refers to information, employees, shareholders, pressure groups, customers.

External Stakeholders. It refers to the partners of the school who have a strong interest in school outcomes but who are not directly involved in the teaching learning process.

Internal Stakeholders. It refers to the partners of the school who are within the school system on a daily basis who largely contribute to the success of the school which include the school head, teachers, and pupils.

Legal Factors. It involves the application of the laws and regulations in the community and other legal issues can affect the educational system such as employment regulations, health and safety regulations.

Political Factors. It refers to those that affect the success of the school – based programs such as policies, laws, and regulations.

Social Factors. It refers to the assessment that affect the involvement of the stakeholders in school – based programs.

Technological Factors. It refers to advancement in terms of technology that optimize internal efficiency which is considered a great asset in educational management and the involvement of the stakeholders in school – based programs.

2. METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the research design, research locale, respondents, research instrument, ethical considerations, data gathering procedure and statistical treatment.

Research Design

The study utilized the mixed method of quantitative and qualitative types of research. It is quantitative because it presented the level of involvement of the stakeholders in school – based programs using the PESTEL framework (political, economic, social, technological, environmental and legal) with the use of a questionnaire. The qualitative method was used on the other aspects of the PESTEL framework using the one-on-one interview with 30 respondents.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in Barangay Gosoon, Carmen, Agusan del Norte which is one of the barangays of the municipality of Carmen, Agusan del Norte where Gosoon Elementary School is situated. It is a part of Sitio Kapatagan, Brgy. Gosoon, Carmen, Agusan del Norte and the only school built for all the school children of Barangay Gosoon. The total population of school is 320 pupils with 10 teachers and a school head.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 30 stakeholders composed of 10 teachers, 10 parents, and 10 barangay officials who were selected purposively using the convenience sampling.

Research Instrument

The questionnaire was the main tool used to determine the involvement of the stakeholders in school – based programs based on the PESTEL framework. It was submitted to the principal and a planning officer for content validation. Some items were refined based on their comments and suggestions. The questionnaire was tried out to the stakeholders of another barangay for its reliability testing using the test-retest method. A focus group discussion was conducted for the qualitative portion where the stakeholders were interviewed on their values and beliefs that helped in the implementation of the school – based projects.

Ethical Considerations

To protect the privacy and welfare of the respondents' opinions on the stakeholders' involvement and level of school-based programs, the researcher held the results of the study confidential. The responses of the participants were respected, and were kept private for the purpose of confidentiality.

Data Gathering Procedure

A formal letter was written to the Division Superintendent to ask permission to conduct a study on the involvement of the stakeholders. Upon its approval, the researcher wrote a letter to the District Supervisor and to the principal to ask permission to allow the researcher to distribute questionnaires to the respondents.

Upon its approval, the researcher scheduled the administration of the questionnaire to the teachers during their break time. The administration of the questionnaire was scheduled in order not to disrupt the classes of the teachers. They were given ample time to answer the questionnaire and after which were retrieved, tabulated, analyzed and interpreted with the use of

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appropriate statistical tools. The parents and barangay officials were grouped together on a scheduled date for the focus group discussion on the influence of their values and beliefs in the implementation of school – based projects.

Statistical treatment

The mean was the statistical tool used to determine the influence of the stakeholders' involvement in school – initiated activities.

The thematic analysis was used for the qualitative part of the study.

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